

IMPACT OF MEDIA RESPONSES AND PUBLIC OUTCRY TO POLITICAL ADS IN INDIA

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Abstract:

The political scenario in India has come a long way, since India got the Independence. Once being a colony under British rule to moving into an independent nation in the year 1947, Indian politics have drastically changed over years. In a current scenario, Indian media has drastically changed over the years with respect to advent of Digital Media. Political ads and political campaigns have increased drastically over the years in India as different political parties are using different media platforms to boost their political campaigns during the election period.

Due to advent increase in social media, today almost all the politicians, celebrities are using social platforms such as Facebook, Twitter etc. Social media is playing an important role in showcasing the political news in a different angle altogether. The classical example was during 2014 and 2019 general elections and as well as Maharashtra elections in the year 2019. Today not only social media but also traditional media such as Television, Newspapers and Radio have played an important role in creating the political ads as well as political campaigns. Lastly it can be concluded that media has a strong impact in creating the political ads and shaping up the public opinion towards a political party.

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Political Advertising

The political advertising scenario in India has gone through an immense evolution. From what used to be a simple form of one-to-one communication, to the new age of political advertising which is more technologically driven, it has become creative, engaging, and

powerful and is no less than how a popular brand promotes itself in the market.

Through the years, political advertising has shifted from a traditional approach to more aggressive technology-based campaigns. It involves the use of various media to reach out to its voters as well as to create a favourable voting preference. Due to the fundamental shift of communication from news to advertising, the public is now exposed to greater amounts of these campaigns during each election cycle. Thus, the use of media forms like television, radio, newspapers, etc. has increased. The significant growth in the political advertising scenario has taken place because of the enlargement of voter's size, technological advancements and their opportunities, and rising competition in Indian politics. Although the content might not be very different from what it used to be, the campaign technique has drastically shifted to experimenting with compelling technology that is around us.

With the emergence of social media, political parties do not shy away from using the platform to their advantage. The digital platforms have become a prominent source of information for all political parties, candidates, and organisations. People are now open about their political views on social media which gives a large picture of the voting behaviour for the parties contesting. While previously, systems were not interactive, new forms of media have made the situation more transparent and approachable.

This new phase of political advertising on digital media requires the sophisticated use of digital technology. It should also have a higher level of interactive information sharing, networking, collaborations, engagement, etc. Keeping an interactive platform is required now more than ever, as people are more interested in their political surroundings and have become alert and careful regarding the powers being bestowed on a single party. People are vocal about their preferences and dislikes and this can be a take away for election advertisers in strategically chalking out a campaign. Taking notes on the social issues, things that matter to the people of the nation, curbing the prevailing social evils are a few points to be taken into account while planning a campaign.

The trend that can be seen taking shape in politics now is more like a B2C industry. That means it will be direct to the voter i.e. the voter wants to hear directly from the politician. The role of media is particularly influenced in this situation. Most news channels run on an advertising-based model. A major chunk comes from the government, where they propagate the party's ideas. Channels failing to do so falls under immense pressure to exist in the race.

It can be seen that the political advertising scenario has evolved for good over time. Something that began as a mere attempt to announce propagandas, has now become a 360-degree strategic mapping of the advertising agencies. Teams from TV advertising agencies and digital marketing agencies that are working towards making the agenda work have to put an all-hands-on-the-deck approach to effectively execute a successful campaign.

<https://itsaugust.com/political-advertising-in-india/>

Examples of Political Advertising in India

Over past few years, due to increase in the usage of social media many political parties are using social media as a marketing tool to enhance the name of their political parties and creating a positive impact on the minds of the people. Social media being considered one of the cheapest modes, due to which a lot of political parties are using social media to create a trust among the public. There is always a tremendous use of social media and different types of social media especially during the election polls.

BJP takes lead in advertising on Google, YouTube with Rs 1.21 cr spend

A week before the first phase of elections, ruling BJP has taken a big lead in advertising on Google and its affiliated platforms such as YouTube with an ad spend of Rs 1.21 crore, while its main rival Congress has spent only Rs 54,100, the search engine said.

Google, in a report on political advertisement across its platforms - Google, YouTube and partner properties, said Rs 3.76 crore was spent by advertisers since February 19.

BJP spent Rs 1.21 crore on advertisements during this period.

TDP's rival YSR Congress of Jagan Reddy was a close third with an ad spend of Rs 1.04 crore.

Congress spent Rs 54,100 on Google platforms.

<https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/elections/lok-sabha/india/bjp-tops-political-advertisers-chart-on-google-rival-congress-ranked-6th/articleshow/68716211.cms?from=mdr>

Digital Politics in India's 2019 General Elections

India's 2019 general election was the first national election contested within a truly digital consumption society, wherein approximately half the voting population had access to digital pathways, and another one-third had access to social media. This article argues that what happens on digital platforms is no longer an externality or an adjunct to offline politics—it is constitutive of it and inseparable from larger political mobilisation.

The 2019 general election shifted paradigms in Indian politics. The more obvious shift was electoral: with the Narendra Modi-led Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) became the first party in 35 years to return to power with an absolute majority that seemed to upend the conventional rules of Indian politics. The elections were also intimately connected to a second societal paradigm shift in India that happened between 2016 and 2019, which, in terms of its political impact, is comparatively less commented upon and is understudied. This is the impact of the rise of a digital data-consumption society driven by the second-highest smartphone penetration in the world (Canalys 2019; PTI 2018b), and the highest average data usage per smartphone, which reached 9.8 gigabytes (GB) per month at the end of 2018 (Ericsson 2019). From the Gutenberg press in medieval Europe to mobile phones of recent history, whenever a new mass technology emerges, it changes the very nature of politics

<https://www.epw.in/engage/article/digital-politics-indias-2019-general-elections>

Conclusion

As the Indian politics have gone through an enormous change in the term of political formation of the government from Indian National Congress to formation of BJP government, citizens of India have seen the roller coaster ride in the history of politics in India. The major changes took place in the year 1990's, wherein the private media channels were introduced into the Indian market that equally played a crucial role in shaping up the Indian politics and changing the opinion of any political issue in current scenario.

Lastly the social media which is also said to be a new age media is playing a predominant role in shaping the politics of a country with a new different way altogether. Although the new age media has a positive as well as negative impact in shaping up the political issue and creating a different perception in the minds of the people.

References

1. <https://itsaugust.com/political-advertising-in-india/>
2. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/elections/lok-sabha/india/bjp-tops-political-advertisers-chart-on-google-rival-congress-ranked-6th/articleshow/68716211.cms?from=mdr>
3. <https://www.epw.in/engage/article/digital-politics-indias-2019-general-elections>